

Hand-cranked tribometer demonstrators made with LEGO™ pieces

Additional materials:

- small weights;
- glass beads;
- and sand paper (or another rough material).

Use

The twin tribometers are designed such that the user can compare different levels of friction. The 6x6 circular tiles that are used as the surfaces are both smooth and the user will experience the same level of friction from both without modification. To modify for difference in friction:

- Option 1: add small weights to the arm above the tip of one of the tribometers will increase the friction of that tribometer;
- Option 2: stick different grades of sandpaper (or another rough material) to the top of the surfaces and replace the LEGO™ tip with a glass bead and glue to increase the longevity;
- Option 3: a combination of options 1 and 2.

As it may be useful to have multiple surfaces, the parts list below contains four 6x6 circular tiles.

Each tribometer has a blank 1x8 white tile that can be used to label the difference between the tribometers.

Tweaks

If you wish to tweak the model, simply download and install BrickLink.com's free design program [Studio](#). Then you can use this program to open the design file for this model: "HandCrankTribometer.io".

We also have more colourful versions of this design, which distinguish the tribometers, to make them easier to discuss.

HandCrankBlue&Orange_NoInstructions.io

HandCrankPurple&Yellow_NoInstructions.io

Parts list

To order this model please see "OrderingLEGO.pdf".

List as .csv file: "HandCrankTribometer.csv".

Image	Description	Item No (& alternate Item Nos)	Colour	Qty
	Plate 1 x 1	3024 28554 30008 63326	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	16
	Plate 1 x 2	3023 6225 28653	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate, Modified 1 x 2 with 1 Stud with Groove and Bottom Stud Holder (Jumper)	15573 78823	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Plate, Modified 1 x 3 with 2 Studs (Double Jumper)	34103	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	12
	Plate 1 x 4	3710	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate 1 x 5	78329	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	8
	Plate 1 x 6	3666	White	8
	Plate 1 x 10	4477	White	4
	Plate 1 x 12	60479	White	2
	Plate 2 x 2	3022 94148	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate 2 x 2	3022 94148	White	4
	Plate 2 x 2 Corner	2420 63325	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Plate 2 x 3	3021 03021	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate, Modified 2 x 3 with 1 x 1 Cutout	73831	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	8

	Plate 2 x 4	3020	5584		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Technic, Plate 2 x 4 with 3 Holes	3709			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate 2 x 8	3034	03034		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Technic, Plate 2 x 8 with 7 Holes	3738			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	6
	Plate 3 x 3	11212			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Plate 4 x 4	3031			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate 6 x 6	3958			Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	2
	Plate 8 x 16	92438			Black	2
	Plate 16 x 16	91405			Black	2
	Plate, Round 1 x 1	6141	4073	30057	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	8
		30057	34823	39799		
		44325	51809	54003		
	Plate, Round 1 x 1 with Open Stud	28626	85861	29387	Black	14
	Plate, Round Half 3 x 6 with 1 x 2 Cutout	18646			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Plate, Round 4 x 4 with Hole	60474			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Plate, Round Corner 5 x 5 Macaroni	80015			Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	8
	Plate, Round 8 x 8 with Hole	74611			Black	2
	Tile 1 x 6	6636	63324	75702	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
		112417				

	Tile 1 x 8	4162	40929		White	2
	Tile, Round 2 x 2 with Hole	15535			Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	10
	Tile, Round Corner 2 x 2 Macaroni	27925 113485	67124	78560	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	40
	Tile, Round Corner 3 x 3 Macaroni	79393	114413		Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	16
	Tile, Round Corner 4 x 4 Macaroni	27507 39725 115121	1939	3477 78885 114655	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	8
	Tile, Round 6 x 6	7212			White	4
	Brick 1 x 1	3005	30071	35382	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Brick 1 x 2	3004	93792		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Brick 1 x 3	3622	45505		Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	12
	Technic, Brick 1 x 3 with Holes	5565			White	12
	Brick 1 x 6	3009	30611		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Technic, Brick 1 x 6 with Holes	3894			Black	4
	Brick 2 x 2 Corner	2357			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Technic, Brick 4 x 6 Open Center	1679	32531	40344	Black	2
	Brick, Round 1 x 1	3062 35390	18860	30068	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	18
	Brick, Round Corner 4 x 4 Macaroni with 3 Studs	48092 72140	10644	15588	Black	8

	Slope 45 1 x 1 x 2/3 Quadruple Convex Pyramid	35344	35343	22388	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	2
	Panel 1 x 2 x 2 - Hollow Studs	87552	35378	94638	Black	6
	Technic Bush 1/2 Smooth	42136	32123		Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	6
	Technic, Pin Connector Round 2L with Slot (Pin Joiner Round)	29219	62462	15555	Black	2
	Technic, Liftarm Thin 1 x 3 - Axle Holes	65123	6632		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Technic, Liftarm, Modified Crank / Pin 1 x 3 - Axle Holes	61408	33299		Black	2
	Technic, Liftarm Thick 1 x 5	32316	41616		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Technic, Liftarm Thick 1 x 7	32524	16615		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Technic, Liftarm Thick 1 x 9	64289	40490		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Technic, Liftarm, Modified L- Shape Quarter Ellipse Thin 3 x 3	65125	32249		Black	4
	Technic, Pin 1/2 with Friction Ridges	89678			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	24
	Technic, Pin 3/4	32002			Brick Yellow or Tan	2
	Technic, Pin with Long Friction Ridges	61332	4459	2780	Black	12
	Technic, Pin 3L without Friction Ridges	39888	32556		Brick Yellow or Tan	16
	Technic, Pin 3L with Friction Ridges and Center Pin Hole	44874	87082		Black	2
	Technic, Axle 3L	4519	32240		Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	2

	Technic, Axle 3L with Stop	24316	Reddish Brown	2
	Technic, Axle and Pin Connector Hub with 2 Axles on Opposite Sides	27940	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	4
	Technic, Axle 5L	32073	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	2
	Technic, Axle 5L with Stop	15462	Reddish Brown	2
	Bar 2L with Stop Ring	78258	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	12
	Technic, Pin 1/2 with 2L Bar Extension (Flick Missile)	42456 61184	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	2
	Technic, Gear 40 Tooth	34432 3649	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	8